

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR AN INCREASED SUPPORT OF CITIZEN SCIENCE IN PORTUGAL

The **European Citizen Science (ECS)**¹ project, funded by the **European Union**, aims to expand and strengthen the Citizen Science (CS) community in Europe through training and awareness-raising activities. Its advocacy goal is to promote the recognition of CS as a powerful tool to support policymaking and a valuable research approach for scientific excellence and sustainable development across Europe.

As part of the project, a series of national events were held with the goal of co-creating policy recommendations to enhance and embed CS into national schemes within EU Member States. On **July 1st, 2025**, the **Portuguese Citizen Science Network (RPCC)**² organized the event “**Ecosistemas de Ciência Cidadã e Políticas Locais-Regionais-Nacionais**” (from the English “**Citizen Science Ecosystems and Local-Regional-National Policies**”) in Lisbon, Portugal. It brought together key stakeholders from across the quadruple helix (4H) (academy, industry, policymakers and citizens) to reflect on the development of CS at the national level and co-create policy recommendations to strengthen its role within the Portuguese research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem.

Participants from academia included **Filipa Bessa** from the University of Coimbra, **Milene Matos** from the University of Aveiro, **Anabela Paula**, Ambassador of the Gigantes Verdes project, **João Reis** from ITQB NOVA, **Inês Sardinha** from the Oeiras Experimenta project, and **Cristina Veiga-Pires** from the University of Algarve, CIMA/ARNET and Centro Ciência Viva of Algarve. From the public sector, **Maria João Leão** (Ciência + Cidadã programme and ITQB NOVA), **Alexandra Vasconcelos** (municipality of Oeiras, in the Science and Innovation Department), and **Paula Vaz** (APA - ARH Algarve) participated in the event. The private sector was represented by **Catarina Azevedo** from INOVA+ and **José Sousa Guedes** from ADER-Sousa. Finally, **Nuno Alves** from APA - ARH Algarve, **Giovanna Dellarole**, citizen of Oeiras, **Henrique Folhas** from Sciaena, and **João Gonçalo Soutinho** from Gigantes Verdes, represented the civil society.

The event fostered effective dialogue, leading participants to identify key challenges and outline measures to advance CS in Portugal. They agreed on the need for an improved **recognition of CS**, beginning with formal support to the Portuguese CS Network (from the Portuguese, Rede Portuguesa de Ciência Cidadã, RPCC), and on **long-term multilevel support for CS infrastructure development and sustainability**, including tax incentives. Participants emphasized promoting CS across sectors, and fostering **professionalisation** and **capacity-building for all stakeholders**, particularly on public engagement and communication. Drawing from their inputs, this policy brief presents **key recommendations to increase CS legitimacy and institutionalisation** in Portugal.

We want to thank all participants for their valuable contributions and input in shaping this policy brief.

¹ European Citizen Science platform <https://citizenscience.eu/>

² Rede Portuguesa de Ciência Cidadã (RPCC) <https://www.cienciacidadada.pt/>

WHAT IS CITIZEN SCIENCE?

As defined by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA): CS, in general, means the **participation of the public in science and research**. It is an open and inclusive approach, with key characteristics including: (1) citizens are actively involved in research; and (2) there is a genuine science outcome, such as new scientific knowledge, conservation action or policy change³.

CS contributes actively to the **democratization** of scientific research by increasing **public awareness** of societal challenges, such as climate change, environmental monitoring or biodiversity conservation, **promoting trust in science and scientific literacy**, while fostering critical thinking and behavioural change. Involving society in research allows for the collection of larger volumes of data, by those who often are the most affected and that at the same time could benefit from, making information more accessible and relevant to real-world needs. This approach amplifies **diverse voices** and ensures that research reflects the concerns of all community members.

METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the event was to co-create policy recommendations tailored to Portugal's R&I context for enhanced support of CS. The event was divided into a theoretical framework presentation and the implementation of a co-creation process focused on understanding 4H stakeholders' **motivations** for engaging with CS, identifying **challenges**, and developing actionable policy **solutions**. The methodology used hereby is based on one the those used in the Mutual Learning Exercise (MLE) on Citizen Science led by the European Commission⁴, following a backcasting planning approach based on an A-B-C-D method developed by The Natural Step Framework, starting with defining future goals (A - Aims & Vision) and working backwards to identify practical steps (C- Creative Solutions and D- Decide on Priorities) towards achieving them based on the country's baseline (B- Baseline Analysis). Both the future goals and the baseline analysis were provided during the theoretical part of the event.

Fig 1. Backcasting in the MLE, following the A-B-C-D method developed by The Natural Step

³ Ten Principles of Citizen Science. <https://www.ecsa.ngo/10-principles/>

⁴ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Gold, M., Arias, R., Haklay, M., Irwin, A. et al., Mutual learning exercise – Citizen science initiatives – Policy and practice – Final report, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/988919>

THE CASE OF PORTUGAL

Citizen participation in scientific research in Portugal has historical roots extending to the 19th century⁵, but more structured efforts began emerging in 2010 as is the case of the **Biodiversity4All**⁶ initiative, which also contributed to the creation of the ECSA. Since then, activities have grown steadily, primarily driven by researchers, universities, research institutions, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and municipal authorities.

A significant step was achieved at the second National CS Meeting in 2019, where stakeholders committed to establishing a collaborative network. The RPCC was formally constituted in 2023, with an elected board assuming a three-year mandate in 2024, providing a focal point for visibility and cooperation across the sector.

CS is referenced in selected policy frameworks, including the National Environmental Education Strategy⁷ (2017), the National Action Plan for Marine Litter⁸ (2024), and annual regional plans of the Azores⁹ (since 2017). However, it remains absent from Portugal's, from the main legislative instrument, the National Law of Science¹⁰, as well as the broader Open Science Policy¹¹ and is not integrated into national strategies for science, education, or innovation.

Dedicated domestic funding mechanisms are not yet in place. While some municipalities, notably Oeiras^{12,13}, provide targeted financial support (with an estimated budget of approximately 300.000€ for the 2020-2025 Oeiras Strategy for Science and Technology), most initiatives depend on integrating activities within broader research projects or securing European funding, particularly through Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects such as ECS, IMPETUS (5 CS projects funded in Portugal with an overall budget of 125.000€)¹⁴, CROPS¹⁵, NEWSERA¹⁶ (12 CS projects with dedicated mentoring and capacity building)¹⁷, and more4nature¹⁸, among others. Their impact at the local, national and international levels can be estimated as economical (new jobs and technologies), environmental (species mapping and protection), policy (reinforced laws), scientific (new data collections, professional networks and peer-reviewed publications), social (inclusion of migrant communities), among others.¹⁹

⁵ Luís C. "A Ciência Cidadã: Passado, Presente e Futuro do Envolvimento Público na Investigação Científica". Revista Lusófona de Estudos Culturais 9 2 (2022): 29-42. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21814/rlec.4051>.

⁶ A biodiversity citizen science project founded in 2010. <https://www.biodiversity4all.org/>

⁷ In Portuguese *Estratégia Nacional de Educação Ambiental (ENEA)* <https://enea.apambiente.pt/>

⁸ In Portuguese *Plano de Ação Nacional para o Lixo Marinho* <https://apambiente.pt/residuos/lixo-marinho>

⁹ In Portuguese *Programa Regional dos Açores* https://portal.azores.gov.pt/programa_do_xiv_governo

¹⁰ In Portuguese Decreto-Lei n.º 63/2019, Diário da República n.º 94/2019, Série I de 2019-05-16, 2466 - 2475 <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/63-2019-122317422>

¹¹ Resolution of the Council of Ministers no. 21/2016. <https://www.ciencia-aberta.pt/en/resolucao-conselho-de-ministros>

¹² Municipality of Oeiras, Portugal <https://www.oeiras.pt/eixo1-educacao-sociedade>

¹³ Municipality of Oeiras, Portugal <https://www.oeiras.pt/-/mais-de-300-mil-euros-para-institui%C3%A7%C3%B5es-no-%C3%A2mbito-da-estrat%C3%A9gia-oeiras-ci%C3%A7%C3%A2ncia-e-tecnologia-2020-2025>

¹⁴ IMPETUS project: <https://impetus4cs.eu/>

¹⁵ CROPS project: <https://www.crops-cs.eu/>

¹⁶ NEWSERA project: <https://newsera2020.eu/>

¹⁷ Navalhas, I, et al. Comunicar ciência cidadã: estratégias dirigidas a diferentes públicos-alvo (accepted in *Análise Social*)

¹⁸ More4nature project: <https://www.more4nature.eu/>

¹⁹ Magalhães, J., et al (2023). NEWSERA Policy Brief 2 (D5.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7752561>

THE CASE OF PORTUGAL

The RPCC and various NGOs serve as the principal drivers of CS activity at the national or local level, though their reliance on voluntary contributions presents significant sustainability challenges. Academic recognition is gradually improving: CS involvement is beginning to factor into research evaluations and recruitment processes, albeit with limited weight. The national research evaluation agency (FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia) has been acknowledging the legitimacy of such practices and is collaborating with RPCC to enhance their standing, while Portuguese organizations participate actively in global reform initiatives, including CoARA²⁰.

Although no comprehensive assessment of scholarly output has been undertaken, publications on CS are increasing in Portugal, spanning biodiversity, environmental studies, social sciences, health, education, and the humanities. But as aforementioned, the enormous potential and expansion of CS as a research field and practice and its community is on the rise. Persistent challenges include the lack of dedicated funding, overreliance on voluntary structures, and the absence of a coherent national strategy. Nevertheless, rising engagement from researchers and policymakers, coupled with the RPCC network's ongoing strategic development, indicates considerable potential for the consolidation and growth of CS in Portugal.

During the event, key 4H stakeholders identified several decisive motivations and challenges, and proposed solutions that serve as basis for the policy recommendations for enhancing CS progress within Portugal's national framework and society.

²⁰ Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is a collective of organisations committed to reforming the methods and processes by which research, researchers, and research organisations are evaluated. <https://coara.eu/>

MOTIVATIONS

Contributing to evidence-based and transformative policies

CS is a critical mechanism for building dialogue and trust amongst stakeholders, facilitating **more democratic, transparent, and evidence-based policies and priority setting**. It is considered instrumental in improving public participation and deliberation in decision-making processes and policy implementation, contributing to capable and transformative public policies. CS also has the potential to **enable shared management and co-creation** of innovative solutions for complex issues (such as those related to environment, urban areas, etc.).

Integrating and creating strong cross-sectors partnerships

CS is perceived as a valuable tool to foster **multidisciplinary, long-term, and strong partnerships**, creating a participatory space where diverse points of view and experiences can be discussed among key stakeholders. Some of these partnerships evolve into **cohesive and relevant networks**, including the creation of institutional CS hubs (taking as example as those piloted under project INCENTIVE²¹). As a result of this process, CS generates social bonds and promotes a **constructive community feeling**.

Fostering knowledge-transfer and mutual learning

CS is recognised as a powerful tool for multi-directional knowledge sharing and mutual learning, enabling the **dissemination of scientific understanding** and the **integration of local, experiential, and academic knowledge** by breaking down knowledge silos. It promotes reciprocity between stakeholders, while **empowering** individuals and valuing them as active contributors in the generation and exchange of knowledge.

²¹ Incentive Project <https://incentive-project.eu/pilot-rpfos/>

MOTIVATIONS

Enhancing scientific excellence and innovation

CS is seen as enhancing scientific excellence through improved **research relevance, data collection and diversification** in terms of locations, composition, environments, and time. It also fosters a shift from problem-centric to **solution-oriented research** and strengthens the **impact and sustainability of scientific results**. At the same time, CS is strongly commended for fostering capacity-building and lifelong learning by bringing science closer to citizens, particularly on environmental issues, resulting in **an improved innovation capacity of all involved stakeholders and opening new perspectives and research questions** for science and society.

Promoting social and human competences and values

CS is widely valued for promoting and embodying key social values such as civic responsibility, ethical engagement, inclusion, and the collective pursuit of a more sustainable, resilient and equitable society. Furthermore, CS initiatives enhance participants' citizenship, future-proof competence and skills - such as critical thinking - through active civic participation and transversal multigenerational mobilisation, with a specific focus on youth engagement. CS is seen as giving voice to the civil society, "believing in the power of citizens", as quoted by a participant.

CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS

Lacking formal recognition from public institutions

Despite its demonstrated benefits, CS continues to face significant barriers due to the **lack of formal recognition, and institutional integration**. Consequently, it suffers a lack of **legitimacy** within research, policy, and societal frameworks, undermining trust and credibility in CS outcomes, and limiting its broader use in scientific research and evidence-informed decision-making. These factors hinder the development and sustainable implementation of CS.

Facing insufficient professionalisation

There is a common concern about the **training, tools, and competences** required to effectively design, manage, and participate in CS. **Gaps in capacity-building and transdisciplinary expertise**, hinder the ability to generate usable evidence. These challenges are compounded by difficulties in aligning timelines, languages, and priorities, often due to unclear expectations and mutual benefits from the outset, as well as a **lack of opportunities for professionalisation**.

Dealing with communication and public engagement gaps

Gaps in dissemination, public engagement, and sustained participation—exacerbated by limited resources and expertise—hinder motivation among participants, already affected by **structural, political, and social issues**, such as the rise of populism, radicalism and disinformation. The **asynchronicity** of stakeholders can be a major challenge, particularly as CS is often built on bringing together “partners with opposing goals”.

Investigating without CS-solid infrastructures

Strict **academic practices**, limited transdisciplinary **human resources**, scarce **scientific instruments for data collection, validation and dissemination** undermines not only CS recognition, but also CS researchers’ daily missions and long-term research. Additional barriers include a **lack of visibility and credibility in traditional research environments**, for which infrastructures are unsuited for CS practice, regarding time management, but also scientific mindsets.

Composing with discontinuous and rigid funding schemes

CS initiatives mainly rely on short-term, project-based funding, hindering long-term continuity, institutional commitment, and project maturation. **Limited financial resources, and insufficient prioritisation in the public agenda** further constrain their sustainability. In this context, maintaining consistent engagement and impact remains challenging.

SOLUTIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Recognising CS as a powerful tool for scientific excellence and social impact

Reaching and adopting a **harmonised definition of CS** - in agreement with ECSA principles - will ensure its formal recognition and enhance its **legitimacy** under the national context. To strengthen its transversal integration into public policy, science and education systems, it is fundamental to **recognise the role of the Portuguese CS Network** as a key and centralised actor, whose role is to inform and communicate to society and other key stakeholders the role, benefits and opportunities of CS. **Formal recognition of CS is further needed at all decision-making levels**, in particular in the education and research policy areas.

Building capacity of all stakeholders to reinforce participatory and democratic values

To increase CS successful impact, stakeholders' training is needed to reach wider audiences and effectively engage with all stakeholders' groups on a long-term perspective. Supporting **capacity-building for stakeholders** means promoting a cross-cutting **participatory culture, enabling dialogue and cooperation between sectors and disciplines**, both at a society, research, industry and policy level. By supporting CS, all sectors **improve their resilience** towards future crises and act together with a democratic instrument using inclusive and **problem-solver oriented participatory strategies**.

Developing programmes for school education and lifelong learning

To foster long-lasting transformations of society towards inclusion and participation, **CS programmes and tools for teachers and educators must be facilitated** for them to actively participate and develop CS projects with **children and youth**. As a crucial contributor to lifelong learning, the **CS sector must be supported to train and inform citizens** about opportunities for participation, thus enhancing their citizenship competences, scientific literacy and critical thinking in a period of lacking trust both in policy and traditional information channels.

Professionalising communication and mediation roles and skills

The **support, in terms of human resources, of communication and engagement positions and valorisation of targeted communication and mediation skills in research centres, universities and the public sector** is decisive to advance an effective communication to multiple CS stakeholders. To this extent, the recognition of the CS consultant or mediator role is crucial. **These professional roles with new future-adapted skills are deeply needed not only to raise awareness on common issues through trans-media communication campaigns**, for example on climate change, create effective engagement strategies and conduct impact evaluation, or to train other professionals to learn how to work collaboratively with multiple stakeholders, such as citizens and policymakers, **further supporting evidence-informed policy advice.**

Fostering collaboration within national networks

The **combined efforts of the RPCC and SciComPT²²**, the national hub for the European Competence Centre for Science Communication²³, as centralising and supporting actors would be key for coordinated communication and dissemination efforts both at **local, regional, national and international level**. Based on their expertise and extended networks, these organizations could further provide accessibility to user-friendly and adapted methodologies and tools, as well as projects' results and best practices across Portugal.

Implementing a multilevel science-informed policy ecosystem to foster trust

CS presents compelling methodologies to associate policymaking, implementation and assessment with scientific evidence, consolidating trust in public decisions. As a first step to reinforce science-informed policy ecosystems, **legislation's adaptation is crucial to enable and legitimize co-creation processes**, supported by the RPCC expertise for the alignment of CS and policymaking, which could happen also with the collaboration of PlanAPP²⁴. Establishing **multi-annual action plans with mandatory social and scientific impact indicators** would ensure a closer cooperation between different stakeholders. Furthermore, fluidifying the **collaboration between different decision-making levels** in Portugal is central. **Creating CS regional and local hubs** can be seen as another relevant step, integrating two main measures: mandating **municipalities to define, pilot and implement framework programmes integrating CS** and data to inform local policies and securing structural funding, fixed as a percentage of municipal budgets and approved by assemblies, independent of political cycles, to both diversify funding and mainstreaming CS culture into all-level policymaking.

²² The Portuguese Network for the Communication of Science and Technology <https://scicom.pt/home>

²³ The European Competence Centre for Science Communication <https://scicommcentre.eu/>

²⁴ The Centre for planning and evaluation of public policies <https://planapp.gov.pt/>

Adapting and reinforcing existing data gathering tools and infrastructures for CS efficient institutionalisation

A centralised national system for data collection should be established, incorporating standardised protocols, auditing, validation, and integration with national and international scientific platforms, and allowing for its articulation with the local and regional CS hubs. This **Citizen Science Data Centre** would guarantee the **validation, quality, and robustness of scientific data**, ensuring its interoperability and use within official databases, including those relevant for **SDG monitoring**. Furthermore, formal mechanisms must be developed to connect CS data with official data-gathering entities and to enhance access to data for all relevant stakeholders. Consolidation of knowledge via **co-authored and open access scientific publications** in CS structuration must be recognized and supported through formal recognition.

Developing and diversifying funding frameworks for CS, including tax incentives

Dedicated, structural funding permitting multi-actor funding schemes (e.g., private sector-academia, public sector-academia, for example from municipalities) must be secured to ensure the long-term sustainability and integration of CS across academia, society, the private and the public sector. At the national level, funding agencies (namely FCT²⁴) should guarantee CS initiatives access to research and innovation public funding. Moreover, **multilevel incentives should be developed and targeted at each sector: for academia, scientific projects** incorporating CS could receive **explicit benefits** in evaluation and funding, including dedicated municipal funding. For other sectors and in coordination with the Ministry of Economy, **tax reductions** should be developed to compensate **citizens volunteering** and non-profit organisations involved in CS projects. Specific tax reductions could also target and benefit companies (e.g. through corporate tax benefits), NGOs or individuals contributing financially, in particular if they are **funding** projects labeled as serving the public interest. Finally, taking into account positive results already achieved, support to **multi-actor joint proposals for EU funding** should be facilitated, particularly those that support bottom-up citizen-led approaches.

²⁴ A Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) é a agência pública nacional que apoia a investigação em ciência, tecnologia e inovação <https://www.fct.pt/>

POLICY BRIEF DETAILS

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